

Conference: Online, 15-18 March 2021
Conference Director: Tristan Loraine
Publisher: London, UK: GCAQE (<https://gcaqe.org>)
Editors: Dieter Scholz, Susan Michaelis

AIRCRAFT CABIN AIR
International Conference 2021

ITF/ETF Perspective of Contaminated Air

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Abstract

Essentially the point of this paper is to express where the [European Transport Workers' Federation \(ETF\)](#) and the [International Transport Workers' Federation \(ITF\)](#) are and why we are supporting the campaign for clean aircraft cabin air.

Keywords

oil fumes, fume event, gas, disease, risk, organophosphates, aircrew, cabin, air, flight safety, aviation, industry

1 Coal Mines Used Canaries – Aircrew: Are They the Canaries of Today?

Canaries were once used in mines to detect odourless gas and being so small and little and frail they would die long before the level of gas became an issue for the miners¹ ([Smithsonian Magazine 2016](#)).

"Seals" is a play on words. Of course, it only works in English. I did check and find that in Spanish the word for a (mechanical) "seal" is not the same as the Spanish word for "seal" that live in the sea and flaps its flippers. A seal as we also know is a mechanical piece of equipment that restricts gases and liquids from moving through different parts of an engine or piece of mechanical engineering. The metaphorical reference to canaries and their crew just leads on to the word seal and why not juxtaposition the word between a mechanical seal and a living creature.

Evidence is compelling the evidence is strong we have people that work on aeroplanes becoming sick. Studies such as the Harvard project indicate that aircrew have a much increased risk of developing certain conditions and diseases than the general population ([McNeely 2018](#), [Harvard T.H. Chan 2018](#)). Some of these conditions are also conditions that are linked to exposure to organophosphates and other chemicals found in oil operating at high temperatures.

¹ See also:

BEAUMONT, Bearnardine, 2019. *Tomb in the Sky – Aviation's Wounded Canaries*. London, UK: Bowker.

Available from: <https://www.amazon.com/dp/0993302548>

LAFAYETTE, Porter, 2017. *Canary in the Cabin*. Available from: <https://aviationtravelwriter.com/2017/04/02/canary-in-the-cabin/>

How to cite this paper (ISO 690, Harvard): MAJOR, Kris, COATES, Eoin, 2021. ITF/ETF Perspective of Contaminated Air. *Aircraft Cabin Air International Conference 2021 (Online, 15-18 March 2021)*. London, UK: GCAQE. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5558490>

Review process: Editorial review. The corresponding author is marked with *.

Now we are not scientists or engineers or doctors this conference has many of those offering in-depth detailed chemistry, biology and physics. I am sure they will offer compelling evidence that will once again reaffirm the absolute need to dig deeper research, more redouble our efforts and not let Covid become a convenient blanket with which to cover this issue.

Not only are we aircrew, but we represent the aircrew. For us this is a really simple series of questions, does oil at very high temperature get in to cabin air through the bleed system? Does the oil that comes in to the cabin air system have a warning on the tin that says inhaling this product when used at high temperatures can lead to death? Are we seeing people with illnesses linked to those chemicals? Are we seeing people die with conditions linked to those warnings?

2 An Artificial Environment

Other than a few warning signs about keeping your seat belt fastened, not to smoke, turn your phone off and the odd sound of bells ringing there is very little and deliberately so to tell you exactly what aircraft is doing to keep you alive (Figure 1).

The truth is, we are in a completely artificial manufactured environment designed to keep a human being alive and make them feel comfortable (Figure 2). Even the lowest of the low cost outfits don't meddle with that.

But we must understand the extent to which the environment that we are working in is lethal to us. Only then can we imagine the complexity of the machinery that makes the environment one we can survive in.

Furthermore, we must also understand that most airlines operate the same aircraft. The industry is savage, competition is fierce, and margins are slim. Therefore, the rules and regulations that we flyby have to be not just minimum standards with no margin for the odd failure or slip.

As we have already heard, there are two distinct issues. One issue is the failure of a mechanical part and a fume event of a varying degree. The other issue is being exposed to low-dose burnt engine oil every single day, the cumulative effects of that over many years. The low-dose cumulative effect is what concerns us so deeply.

Figure 1: Air travel as we experience it.

Figure 2: Air travel as it is.

3 Dangerous Chemicals

Already the science of this campaign has taken us on a journey, and it has led to new revelation (Figure 3). We have found that there are certain people with certain DNA that will react worse than most. We will find more evidence that proves or goes beyond reasonable doubt – reasonable medical doubt – that the chemicals that aircrew are breathing in, day after day, after day are affecting their health.

Figure 3 Only a selection of presentations delivered by scientists at the Aircraft Cabin Air International Conference.

We have so many young women working in this industry at the point of which they are most likely to have children and they being exposed to these gases. No, I don't know whether or not it is because I work in an industry with lots of women that we hear of so many having issues and problems with pregnancy from miscarriages, stillbirths, inability to get pregnant and even losing babies? Or there is a problem that this industry is creating?

Depression and mental illness is commonplace in this industry. Now I know that we are as a society becoming more aware of mental illness, however, I am still seeing increasing numbers of people that need mental clinical help.

This is the 21st-century we do not need to risk other human being's health. Commercial aviation is a relatively new business; therefore we are only just seeing the long-term effects of being in this industry (Figure 4). We are only just having people have a 40 year career. We're only just seeing people in retirement developing illnesses in greater numbers. We have known that the chemicals that we are using are dangerous. The only question is by how much can we be exposed, really?

Low Dose exposure – what are we seeing?

- A long flying career spent breathing engine bleed air with LOW DOSE exposure
- A short career during the most common years for children

Figure 4: Long term effects of chemical exposure.

Are we looking at this properly? We know the chemicals when inhaled are dangerous. The only question is how much. And are there alternatives to not breathing in these chemicals? Yes, there are. History will judge the people that think they are very clever, very big, very wise, and the ones with all the excuses to say "no, we must carry on there is nothing to see here".

We have systems that prevent human beings from being exposed to these chemicals. There is no real reason on this planet to prevent applying these systems. What we suspect is that it is about lawyers, about litigation and cost which prevents these systems to be used.

4 Delays Again and Again

Look we all know that there are companies designing sensors and filters. We know that they can be retrofitted. We know that they will work.

Is it beyond reason that what is actually happening here is delay, the tactics of delay!

This is an industry issue not just an individual operator issue, whilst individual operators are faced with this. There isn't global proactive direction from the bodies as it should be. So, we will continue to see the industry do everything they can to push a solution of the problem into the future.

As a pragmatist you would say: How can we confirm there is a problem? And: Do we have a solution? This is a multibillion dollar industry. Can we conceivably stop people flying, if there is a problem and we do not have a solution? Well, yes, we just have – look what has happened with Covid.

I feel that industry and regulators are employing drag anchors to slow down a solution. The application of sensors and filters seem like an opportunity to make this a historical issue only. The future is safe and we can hand this over to scientists and lawyers to thrash this out for years to come. And whilst that might seem preferable particularly because fume events might be rarer and therefore not as many passengers will be affected – it doesn't fully resolve the problem of low dose, continual exposure. The crew again are Canaries being exposed to fumes until the science can catch up and be accepted as damaging to our health.

Every day we delay, more aircraft roll off the production line with bleed air systems. Each aircraft means 20 years or more to contaminate aircrew just beginning their careers.

Cost aside, there is little reason for doing anything other than changing the cabin air we breathe by changing how it is provided onboard.

5 Conclusion

With the evidence we have seen over the years, it is difficult to suggest we as ETF and the ITF shouldn't be supporting this campaign for clean cabin air with everything we have.

I have been flying for over 22 years – I hear an awful lot of counter evidence based on a lack of science, or inconclusive data, or new research instigated by industry, or regulators have not detected anything we should worry about.

In 22 years and my position that puts me in contact with crew all over the world, I have not heard a single crew member tell that they have been involved in any major study aimed at looking at their health relating to this topic from any source other than by unions and groups worried about the effects of cabin air quality. I am not suggesting that industry has not undertaken serious studies, only that the data I have seen presented by the concerned groups is far more compelling and comprehensive.

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